

Application of Physical Geomorphometry in Digital Geomorphological Mapping

Anton B. Popov

Faculty of Geography
MSU-BIT university
Shenzhen, P.R. China
antonmsu1117@gmail.com

Jozef Minár

Department of Physical Geography and Geoinformatics
Comenius University
Bratislava, Slovak Republic
jozef.minar@uniba.sk

1

Abstract— This study builds on the principles of physical geomorphometry, focusing on the relationship between gravitational energy and geomorphometric variables. We applied a modified version of the algorithm for physically-based elementary land surface segmentation which also integrates dynamic least squares (DLS) generalization and GEOBIA. The modified algorithm produced plausible and genetically interpretable results in both areas, reinforcing the value of physical geomorphometry for geomorphological mapping. Additionally, we introduced the concept of a physical-geomorphometric signature, which proved highly effective for quantitatively comparing different genetic groups of landforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Geomorphological maps are an essential resource for numerous applications related to land surface studies. Enhancing these maps by integrating geomorphometric approaches with spatial data science techniques significantly improve their accuracy and utility. While machine learning algorithms have become a key tool in this process, their inherent limitations prevent them from serving as a standalone solution for geomorphological mapping. Instead, they function more effectively as a complementary approach.

Physical geomorphometry (PG), on the other hand, is uniquely suited to address these challenges. By directly linking geomorphometric variables to gravitational energy, PG enables land surface partitioning that adheres not only to the principle of regionalization—ensuring internal homogeneity and external differentiation—but also to fundamental physical laws. This integration enriches the resulting segments with deeper geomorphological significance, providing a more robust foundation for interpretation and analysis.

In this paper, we build upon the elementary physically-based land surface segmentation proposed in [1], and the extension of its application to the diverse topographies of karst and glacial landscapes in [2]. This adaptation underscores the versatility and potential of PG in advancing geomorphological mapping techniques.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study areas

The study was conducted in Slovakia across two contrasting topographies: Malá Studená Dolina (58.4 ha) and the Silická planina Plateau (217 ha). The first located in the Tatra Mountains (2,066–2,516 m a.s.l.), represents a classic Pleistocene glacial cirque. The second, Silická planina Plateau, part of the Slovak Karst (404–568 m a.s.l.), is one of Europe’s most distinctive karst landscapes.

B. DEM generalization and segmentation

To optimize (generalize) the DEM we applied the dynamic least squares method [3]. A fixed fourth-order polynomial, and flexible the moving window size was used. This process resulted in the computation of nine physical-geomorphometric variables suitable for elementary segmentation according [1]: elevation, slope and aspect, three curvatures (normal slope and contour line curvatures $(k_n)_s$ and $(k_n)_c$, and torsion curvature $(\tau_g)_c$) and three changes of curvatures (normal and contour change of $(k_n)_c - (k_n)_{cs}$ and $(k_n)_{cc}$, and normal change of $(k_n)_s - (k_n)_{ss}$). The multiresolution segmentation of geographical object-based image analysis (GEOBIA) of the territories was done in the eCognition software using ESP 2 tool [4] with increment of step size of 5 (more in [2]). The resulting generalized DEMs and segmentations used are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Generalized DEMs and segmentations of study areas: A – Malá Studená Dolina (part of the glacial cirque in the rectangle); B – Silica (part of the karst plateau). According [2], modified.

C. Physical-geomorphometric analysis

The PG concept was applied to assess segmentation results and classify landforms. It was done in few stages. At the first stage, we computed mean values of various PG indices for elementary forms using the generalized DEM and a segmentation results. For indices with negative values, absolute values were also calculated. Coefficients of variance of i input variables (CV_i) quantifies the affinity of a derived segment to the homogeneity (constant value) of these variables. According to [1] we computed the magnitude of this affinity as $Af_i = 1 - (CV_i)/2$. The range of the index lies in interval $\langle 0,1 \rangle$ (if Affinity < 0 , affinity is considered zero). Expert-based morphogenetic classification of segments preceded the next step of PG analysis. This aggregated PG indices for each morphogenetic landform type by filtering out outlier pixels beyond the standard deviation and normalizing the remaining values to a 0–100 scale (or -100 to +100 for indices with both positive and negative values). The normalized data was used to produce box plot graphs (Fig. 2), hierarchically describing the geomorphic energy influencing each landform type. The position of a landform determines its global (GGE) and regional (RGE) geomorphic energy, related to the elevation above sea level or local basis of erosion. Due to their strong correlation in small areas, only GGE was used. Local geomorphic energy related to diffusion processes ($PESD$) is defined by mean curvature, while energy associated with mass flow (PES) is determined by slope sine. Gravity-concordant profile and plan curvatures ($(k_n)_s$ and $(k_n)_c$) directly influence PES , causing flow acceleration ($\Delta PES(k_n)_s$) or concentration ($\Delta PES(k_n)_c$).

Figure 2. PG signature concept: Mean and range of regionally normalized values (100 = max) of PG indices (A). Mean of energies with positive and negative values (B). After [2].

The combined effect of these curvatures is represented by excess energy (PES_e) determined by difference curvature. In contrast, twisting curvature ($(\tau_g)_c$) captures gravity-discordant changes in PES ($\Delta PES(\tau_g)_c$) that do not affect local flow, reflecting the influence of external regulators beyond diffusion or mass flow. Finally, integral curvature energy ($IPESC$) quantifies the total energetic impact of all curvatures, providing a comprehensive measure of the landform's energetic behavior.

The absolute values of energies with both positive and negative components ($PESD$, $\Delta PES(k_n)_s$, $\Delta PES(k_n)_c$, PES_e) indicate the significance of energy within a landform type, similar to purely positive energies. A smaller range of values on Fig.2 A indicates a more specific characteristic for the landform type. The ratio of curvature energy to slope (PES) reveals the relative role of curvature in the landform signature. The normalized energy values forming the PG signature, which reflects the balance or dominance of positive (destructive) and negative (constructive) geomorphic energy, are visualized in Fig. 2B. This energy significance curve highlights both positive and negative extreme values, which indicate instability and values close to zero reflect equilibrium.

III. RESULTS

In the territory of Malá Studená Dolina we distinguished 7 morphogenetic types of landforms, namely: Cirque headwall, Morain, Morain residue, Preglacial surface, Sheepback, structural linear feature and Talus landform (Fig. 3). The Silica area was classified to five basic landforms (Fig. 4): Karst plateau dissected, karst plateau smooth, Slope on lithological boundary, Tectonic window and tectonic window sinking transition landform.

Figure 3. Digital geomorphological map of Malá Studená Dolina – Modified from [2].

Figure 4. Digital geomorphological map of Silica – expert-based classification of automatically delineated elementary forms. Modified from [2].

The affinity of these segments to ideal elementary forms (EF) in Malá Studená Dolina is predominantly driven by the combination of slope and aspect (Fig. 5, upper left), a characteristic feature of mountainous landscapes. This relationship is further emphasized by an exceptionally high magnitude of affinity observed across the area (Fig. 5, upper right). Notably, the large boulder situated at the center of the area, along with certain structural linear features, exhibits the highest affinity to an EF type characterized by a combination of slope and $(k_n)_c$.

In Silica, the affinity predominantly aligns with two types of EF: constant altitude (horizontality) and the combination of constant slope and aspect (linearity) (Fig. 5, lower left). This dominant affinity is evident across the majority of the territory, with only a

few isolated segments displaying low affinity magnitudes (Fig. 5, lower right). Overall, the magnitude of affinity to equilibrium elementary forms in the case of the Silica area is significantly lower, which may be characteristic of the karst topography formed more by chemical denudation than by gravity processes.

Figure 5. Affinity of real segments to equilibria forms (left) and magnitude of this affinity (right) for Malá Studená Dolina (upper part) and Silica (lower part). The contour line interval is 20 and 10 meters respectively.

Figure 6. PG signature of moraine segments of Malá Studená Dolina study area. The PG signature of landform types in Malá Studená Dolina effectively differentiates them and highlights the physical basis of

their geometric variations. However, in this study, we focus on a single landform for both Malá Studená Dolina and Silica. In the first territory, the energy balance curve for the moraine landform (Fig. 6, upper right) is surprisingly stable, contrary to expectations of imbalance caused by the abrupt deposition of moraine material on the surface.

Figure 7. PG signature of tectonic window of Silica study area

PG analysis at the segment level reveals that while half the segments show imbalance, the others exhibit equilibrium, likely due to underlying factors. Fig. 6 (lower part) highlights two groups: segment 24 (lower left) represents a balanced state, likely due to thinner glacial material and additional gravitational remodelling in the valley bottom, while segment 48 (lower right) represents the most significant signature of the landform.

In Silica (Fig. 7), PG graphs for the Tectonic Window landform reveal extremely low positional energy (GGE) and generally low other energies (Fig. 7, upper right). Some segments exhibit energetic balance, with segment 43 being the most representative (Fig. 7, lower left). Conversely, segments in the valley bottom are characterized by high $\Delta PES(\tau_g)_c$. Values, reflecting the significant influence of streams as regulators of adjacent development, primarily determined by $(\tau_g)_c$ and indirectly by $\Delta PES(\tau_g)_c$. This is illustrated by the balance curve of segment 44 (Fig. 7, lower right).

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

In digital geomorphological mapping, it is essential to delineate geomorphic units that are both genetically and geometrically homogeneous. Our method achieves this by emphasizing unique morphogenetic interpretations for each segmented area. By integrating the concept of physical geomorphometry (PG), we

extended the approach of [5] to identify unique landform signatures.

For the first time, "signature" refers not only to statistical morphometric measures but also to the physical significance of landforms. While this is a pilot study, it lays the groundwork for further theoretical and applied advancements.

In this framework, landform type signatures can be compared with individual segment signatures (Figs. 6, 7), enabling the identification of genetic variations, reclassification of segments, or recognition of polygenetic origins. PG analysis also highlights uncertainties and variations in genetic classifications, refining our understanding of landform types and their evolution.

PG analysis proves invaluable for characterizing landforms, offering insights into the physical processes shaping them and improving the accuracy of geomorphological mapping. It identifies subtle features and patterns often overlooked by traditional methods, bridging the gap between qualitative observations and quantitative assessments, and advancing landform studies with a robust analytical framework.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was funded by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under contract No. APVV-22-0024. We sincerely thank the research team at Pavol Jozef Šafárik University, particularly doc. Michal Gallyay, for providing the data for the Malá Studená Dolina and Silica study areas.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Minár, L. Drăguț, I. Evans, R. Feciskanin, M. Gallyay, M. Jenčo, & A. Popov, 2024. Physical geomorphometry for elementary land surface segmentation and digital geomorphological mapping. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 248, 104631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2023.104631>
- [2] A. B. Popov, J. Minár, L. Drăguț, 2025, Physically-based digital geomorphological mapping: Case study of glacial and karst topography. *Geomorphology*, Vol. 470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2024.109539>
- [3] J. Minár, J. Minár Jr., & I. S. Evans, 2015. Towards exactness in geomorphometry. In: Jasiewicz, J., Zwoliński, Z., Mitasova, H., Hengl, T. (Eds.), *Geomorphometry for Geosciences*. Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland, pp. 27–30. *Geomorphometry 2015 Conference Proceedings*.
- [4] L. Drăguț, O. Csillik, C. Eisank, & D. Tiede, 2014, Automated parameterisation for multi-scale image segmentation on multiple layers. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 88, 119–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2013.11.018>
- [5] R. J. Pike, 1988, The Geometric Signature: Quantifying Landslide-Terrain Types from Digital Elevation Models I. *Mathematical Geology* 20(5), 491–511. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00890333>